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Extraction and Characterization of Natural Fibre from Fishtail Palm Tree Trunk for Utilization in Polymer Process

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ABSTRACT

The emergent global challenge of the use of synthetic fibres and the demand for eco-sustainable materials necessitate the development of natural fibres from plants, animal and mineral sources. Synthetic fibres, though mechanically superior, remain expensive and environmentally non-biodegradable. This study investigates the extraction and characterization of fishtail palm tree trunk fibre (FTPTF) as a potential eco-friendly material for industrial applications. The central problem addressed is the poor utilization of agroforestry residues and the lack of viable methods for converting waste to high-value materials. Specifically, the study aimed to extract, characterize and evaluate the physico-mechanical, thermal, and morphological properties of fishtail palm trunk fibre. FTPTF was extracted via water retting. Mechanical testing (ASTM standards) revealed that tensile strength (210 MPa), presents a 50% improvement. FTIR analysis revealed characteristic peaks corresponding with O-H, C-H, C=C suitable for chemical bonding while scanning electron microscopy (SEM) confirmed strong irregular protrusions which increase the effective contact area. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) indicated an improved thermal stability, with onset near (147.7 °C) while Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) showed an increase in crystallinity from 58% to 63%, confirming the nucleating of FTPTF. The study infers that, fishtail palm trunk fibre is a viable reinforcement for polymeric materials such as in the production of composites with superior mechanical strength, thermal stability. It is recommended that future research should focus on advanced fibre surface modification to enhance interfacial adhesion, long-term durability.

Keywords: Extraction, Characterization, Natural fibre, Fishtail Palm tree trunk, Utilization Polymer process.

INTRODUCTION

The use of synthetic fibres have over-time cost so many industries leading to the quest for alternative sources of fibre. Agro forestry waste have been under- utilized which could be an alternative source of fibre to cost-effective synthetic fibres. According to Ribeiro, et al. (2023), natural fibres have been used to recycle the majority of post-consumer plastics in an effort to lessen the influence that these plastics have on the environment. In addition to the utilization of novel polymers derived from renewable

resources, the mechanical advantages of polymers combined with natural fibres have caught the interest of numerous researchers (Mohanty, et al., 2022). Gupta, et al. (2022) state that industrial waste, agroforestry wastes, or waste biomass can be used to generate natural fibres. This type of lignocellulosic reinforcement can help create composites that are very beneficial to the environment. These resources can also be used specifically to lessen the environmental constraints that underlie a linear economy (Sharma, et al., 2021).

According to Ajayi, et al. (2024), legalizing the upgrading and repurposing of various industrial and agroforestry wastes helps to move the economy from a linear to a circular one, which tries to reduce waste and encourage the sustainable use of natural resources, through more innovative product design, longer use, recycling and more, as well as regenerate nature (Asyraf, et al., 2022). The fundamental shift in material science is this shift from the idea of waste removal to the idea of turning wastes into materials with high added value (Arevalo-Gallegos, et al. 2017).

The new trend of research has highlighted the importance of these fibres on the polymer to produce a composite (Nijjar, et al., 2024). Previous research has evaluated these fibres' effects on the composites, including their mechanical, features of durability, shrinkage, impact strength, and fracture energy. Tshifularo, (2017) stated that the uneven cross-section and non-uniformity of natural fibres set them apart from synthetic fibres like glass, polypropylene, and polyolefin. The ability of fibres to act as a filler in the polymeric matrix is responsible for its reinforcement capability. Recent years have seen the development of new materials made from bio-sourced wastes, such as particle-filler polymers including fibres like flax, banana, pineapple leaf, jute, and so on (Zhang, et al., 2018).

These bio-sourced fibres are renewable and sustainable (Weyhrich, et al., 2023), it is eco-friendly and reduces dependence on synthetic fibres. Because composites constructed from these natural fibres are biodegradable and have better mechanical qualities, Praveena, et al., (2022) revealed that bio-composites offer a solution to the recycling issues of glass and carbon fibres-reinforced plastics. In many applications, lower-density composites are becoming viable substitutes for carbon and glass-reinforced composites (Mohammadi, et al., 2022). Composite reinforced with natural fibres are particularly sought-after because of their lower cost in sectors like automotive and transportation (Skosana, et al., 2025). Furthermore, lignocellulosic materials the primary waste from some food industries and agroforestry have the potential to give polymers reinforcing qualities because of their accessibility, lightweight, biodegradable, renewable, and cost-effective (Leite-Barbosa, et al., 2024).

The findings of this research work suggest that Fishtail palm tree could be used as a viable source of natural fibre in composite and other industrial applications. This study aimed at extracting fibre from Fishtail palm trunk by water retting and to carry out physico-chemical, mechanical parameters and characterize the fibre using SEM, TGA/DSC and FTIR

Materials and methods

Materials: Distilled water, bowl, wooden hammer, axe, knife, weighing balance, Pelkin Elmer 3000 MX FTIR spectrophotometer

Preparation of natural fibre from fishtail palm tree trunk

The process outlined by Vijayalakshmi et al. (2023) was employed in the preparation of the natural fibres with slight modification, after cutting and separating the fibre source from the main stem of the fishtail palm trunk (parent plant), it was brought to boiling for 1hr after which the fibre source was submerged in water for a week and observed at 24 hrs intervals observing the microbial degradation activities that loosen the gum-like materials tightly holding fibers. After the degradation process, the stalks were mechanically beaten with a wooden hammer. The extracted fibre was washed under running water to remove excess impurities and non - fibrous materials. The fibre was then submerged in water for 3 days to degrade the remaining non - fibrous materials. The extracted fibre was air - dried and stored for further analysis and use.

Cellulose content

0.1 g of the fibre samples were weighed into a beaker and treated with 20 cm³ of sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) to dissolve the non-cellulosic components and leaving cellulose residue. After 30 mins, the solution was

washed with distilled water and filtered using pre-dried filter paper. The residue was dried in an oven set at 105°C, cooled in a desiccator until constant weight was achieved. This procedure was repeated 3 times and average value was determined (Thandavamoorthy, et al., 2023).

$$\% \text{ Cellulose} = \frac{\text{Weight of dried residue}}{\text{Weight of initial sample}} \times 100$$

Where; weight of the dried residue = (weight of the filter paper + residue) - weight of the filter paper.

Lignin content

A dried grind fibre was weighed at 0.1 g into a beaker, 25 cm³ of H₂SO₄ was measured and transferred into the beaker. The solution was boiled for 30 mins in a water-bath to remove non-lignin compounds in the sample. After filtering, the residue was washed with distilled water and dried in an oven at 105°C until a constant weight was achieved. After three iterations of this procedure, an average was calculated (Sweygers, et al., 2022).

$$\% \text{ Lignin} = \frac{\text{Weight of dried residue}}{\text{Weight of initial sample}} \times 100$$

Hemicellulose Content

A method described by Kabir, et al., (2021) was used. A dried ground sample of the fibre was weighed at 0.1 g into a clean and dried beaker. 05 cm³ of Neutral Detergent Solution (NDS) was measured and added into the beaker to dissolve hemicellulose and some other components. The solution was filtered using pre-weighed filter paper and the residue collected was weighed as W_i. The residue was again treated with acid detergent to dissolve the remaining protein and ash. The leftover ADF residue was then placed into a known weighed crucible using spatula and dried in the oven at 50 °C. To extract the ash content and eliminate organic matter, the dried crucible and residue were burned for 3 hours at 600°C in a muffle furnace.

$$\% \text{ Hemicellulose} = \frac{\text{Weight of hemicellulose}}{\text{Weight of initial sample}} \times 100$$

Where; weight of the hemicellulose =: weight of NDS residue - (weight of ADF residue + weight of ash)

Ash content

A sample of ground fibre was weighed and recorded as W_o as initial weight. After cleaned and dried in an oven at 105°C for an hour, the crucible was allowed to cool in a desiccator before being weighed as W_c. The weighed sample were transferred into a. The crucible containing the sample was heated to 550 °C in a muffle furnace for 3 hrs. After 3 hrs, the crucible cooled in a desiccator and weighed again as W_a (AOAC, 2016). This process was repeated 3 times to an average value (Chokshi, et al., 2022).

$$\% \text{ Ash} = \frac{W_a - W_c}{W_o} \times 100$$

Where; W_a is weight of the crucible + sample after ash

W_c is weight of the crucible

W_o is weight of the sample before ash

Moisture content

A crucible was cleaned, dried in an oven that was set at 50°C for an hour, and then allowed to cool in a desiccator. The dry crucible was then cleaned, and its empty weight was noted as W_o. A representative

sample of 5.0 cm fibre was measured using ruler and weighed with the crucible W_1 . The weighed sample was dried in an oven for 1 hr at 105 °C allowed to cool in desiccator and weighed W_2 . These processes continued until the weight remained constant (Vijay, et al., 2021).

$$\% \text{ Moisture} = \frac{W_2 - W_0}{W_1 - W_0} \times 100$$

Where; W_0 is weight of empty crucible

W_1 is weight of crucible + sample before drying

W_2 is weight of crucible + sample after drying

Water absorption

A method described by Abd Halip, et al., (2019) was adopted. An empty, clean and dry beaker was weighed and recorded as W_1 . A representative sample of 5 cm fibre was measured and weighed into a beaker with distilled water at a marked point, the sample was left to soak for 24 hrs at room temperature. After being fully submerged in water. The fibre was gently removed using tweezers and damp with towel to remove without squeezing the fibres, the wet fibre was weighed and recorded as W_2 . The fibres sample was dried in an oven set at 105 °C for two hours and was weighed as W_3 .

$$\% \text{ Water absorption} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_3 - W_1} \times 100$$

Where;

W_1 is the weight of the empty beaker

W_2 is the weight of empty beaker + sample prior to drying

W_3 is weight of empty beaker + sample after drying

Density

Density measurement was carried out by displacement method where a dry measuring cylinder was filled with distilled water to a marked point (V_0). 5 cm bundle of the fibres were measured and were inserted into the cylinder, the change in volume was recorded as (V_1). This process was repeated three times to get an average value (Amiri, et al., 2017).

Linear Density

The method as described by Mahmud, et al. (2022) was adopted. A precise length of fibre (10 cm) was measured using a calibrated ruler and recorded as (L). Care was taken to ensure the fibre was laid flat without tension or curvature during measurement. The mass of each fibre sample was determined using an analytical balance with a sensitivity of 0.0001 g and recorded as (W). Samples were weighed in triplicate to ensure accuracy, and the average mass was recorded. The average length was converted to (m) by multiplying the length by 0.001. The linear density (tex) was calculated;

$$\text{Linear Density (tex)} = \frac{W \times 1000}{L(m) \times n}$$

The results were expressed in Tex (grams per 1,000 meters), a standard unit in textile engineering.

Where:

W is the weight of the fibre sample (g)

L is the average length of fibres (m)

n is the number of fibres measured for the average length

Tensile strength

According to ASTM C1557-14, the produced sisal fibres' tensile strength, Young's modulus, and elongation at break were determined at room temperature (25 °C) and 55% relative humidity

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FTIR was performed in the samples isolated to have a prompt result regarding the bio mineral. A few crystals were mixed with KBr (Merck for spectroscopy) and pulverized in an agate mortar to form a homogenous powder from which, under a pressure of 7 tons, the appropriate pellet was prepared. All spectra were recorded from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} using the Pelkin Elmer 3000 MX spectrometer. Scans were 32 per spectrum with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . The IR spectra were analyzed using the spectroscopic software Win-IR Pro Version 3.0 with a peak sensitivity of 2 cm^{-1} .

a

b

c

Plate1: (a) Fishtail palm trunk, (b) Prepared fishtail palm trunk (c) Fishtail palm fibre

Results and discussions

Composition of Fishtail palm trunk fibre

The chemical composition of *Caryota uren* L. (FTPTF) may vary due to some factors which may include climate, soil properties, plant parts and age as well as extraction conditions. In this study, the result reveals cellulose content of (60.05 wt%), lignin (12.12 wt%), hemicellulose (14.03 wt%), wax (0.72 wt%) and ash (3.81 wt%). The major component of plant fibre is the cellulose which contributes to properties such as tensile strength, stiffness and contributes in various chemical and mechanical interlocking and reactions (Sivananthan et al). the cellulose content recorded for this work was lower than fibres like Baobab bast which was recorded as 60.70 wt%. A lignin content of 12.12 wt% shows a higher lignin content compared to (5.19) wt% recorded by Eltahir et al., (2021). The presence of lignin influences the structural morphology and contributes to the rigidity of the fibre. Kumar et al (2023) recorded lignin content of Baobab bast L (8.33), Fishtail palm (9.12) (Sivanantham et al., 2024) and a higher lignin (21 wt %) was reported by Dawit et al., (2020). Wax content fall within the moderate content of (0.5 – 2 wt%). High wax content could obstruct the fibre-matrix bonding process especially in composite processing.

Physical properties of Fishtail palm trunk fibre

The fibre analyzed shows a density of 1.31 g/cm^3 . The value aligns with the findings (1.32 g/cm^3) of Prithivirajan et al., (2020). Lower than the the stem of *Parthenium hysterophorus* (1.47 g/cm^3) as reported by Vijay et al. (2021) but higher than the values (1.25 g/cm^3) reported by Khan et al., (2021). The expansion of cellulose and the dissolution of other substances including lignin, wax, and hemicellulose may be the cause of an increase in density (Gapsari et al., 2021). Linear density (3.3 tex), moisture content (11.42) and water absorption (60.42). The result obtained coincide with the report of Sabarinathan et al. (2020). A low water absorption and moisture content can be beneficial for applications where dimensional stability and resistance to moisture induced degradation are important.

Mechanical properties of Fishtail Palm Fibre

The fibre shows a tensile strength of (210 MPa), E-modulus (2.5 GPa), and Elongation at break (5%). The result shows lower value of tensile strength compared to (249.23 MPa) as presented by Sivanantham et al., (2024) and a lower value in elongation at break (2.01 %) for Fishtail palm fibre. But shows some more improved mechanical properties than Vetiver fibre with tensile strength (204.34 MPa), elongation at break (2.21) (Jena et al., 2022). Fibres with high tensile strength and modulus can

withstand stress and strain, ensuring the longevity of the products in applications textiles, composite and rope processing (Katragadda, et al., 2022).

FT-IR analysis

Figure 1 reveals the FT-IR of untreated FTPT fibre, the result reveal more or less functional groups on the surface of the fibre, showing characteristic absorption bands in the mid-infrared region, particularly between 4000 cm^{-1} and 600 cm^{-1} . A broad peak around 3400 cm^{-1} is typically attributed to O–H stretching vibrations (Iskandar, et al., 2022), indicating the presence of hydroxyl groups in cellulose and hemicellulose. This band reflects the hydrophilic nature of the fiber (Thandavamoorthy et al., 2023) and its potential for hydrogen bonding with polymer matrices. A smaller peak near 2900 cm^{-1} corresponds to C–H stretching of aliphatic groups, commonly found in the cellulose backbone and lignin structures (Kalita et al., 2024).

In the fingerprint region ($1800\text{--}800\text{ cm}^{-1}$), several key peaks are observed. A band near 1730 cm^{-1} is often associated with C=O stretching in ester or carboxylic groups (Parre, et al., 2020), which may originate from hemicellulose or residual pectin. The presence of a peak around 1600 cm^{-1} suggests aromatic C=C stretching, indicative of lignin content. These features confirm that water retting retains a significant portion of the fiber's native lignocellulosic structure (Balasubramani, et al., 2024). Loganathan et al. (2024) reported that, FTIR analysis of Fishtail palm tree stem fibers also revealed similar bands, supporting the presence of cellulose and lignin as dominant constituents. Additional peaks between 1200 cm^{-1} and 1000 cm^{-1} correspond to C–O–C and C–O stretching vibrations, which are characteristic of glycosidic linkages in cellulose.

Figure 1: FT-IR analysis of untreated FTPTF

SEM images of untreated FTPTF

Scanning electron micrographs of the untreated FTPTF reveal a non-uniform, irregular surface. At $9,000\times$ and $10,000\times$ magnification, the fiber might have been sheathed in a residual cuticle of waxes and pectin (Palaniappan, et al., 2025), with patches of hemicellulose still occluding underlying cellulose fibrils. These topographical features create a high-surface-energy, roughened profile compared to the smooth, wax-coated fiber core (Sai et al., 2023). Such morphology directly influences adhesion to a non-polar polymer matrix composite processing. The grooves and pits present on the surface allow molten polymeric materials to flow into the voids surface (Vinod, et al., 2019) during processing, solidifying into micro-anchors that resist pull-out improving mechanical interlocking (Lau et al., 2018).

Figure 2: SEM images of untreated FTPTF: **(a)** Magnification at 9,000x **(b)** Magnification at 10,000x

Figure 3: reveals thermal analysis of untreated FTPTF. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) of untreated fiber. The DSC trace of the untreated fibre exhibits two endothermic peaks at approximately 165.8 °C and 192.3 °C, with an onset near 147.7 °C ($\Delta H \approx 4.64$ J/g) and a secondary onset around 183.4°C. The first peak corresponds to the evaporation of bound and loosely held moisture alongside the melting of low-molecular-weight extractives (waxes, pectins, residual hemicellulose) (Hassan et al., 2020). The energy absorbed reflects the disruption of hydrogen bonds and van der Waals interactions within these amorphous constituents (Nurazzi, et al., 2021). The second, smaller endotherm is attributed to the initial thermal degradation of hemicellulose and amorphous cellulose chains (Asyraf, et al., 2023), which require higher enthalpic input to cleave glycosidic bonds. Such dual transitions are characteristic of raw lignocellulosic fibers (Li, 2021) containing substantial amounts of non-crystalline polysaccharides and extractives (Sivanantham et al., 2024).

The TGA curve shows three principal mass-loss stages. Stage I (30–150 °C), ~ 5 wt% loss, reflecting desorption of free and bound water and volatilization of extractives such as waxes and low-molecular-weight acids (Ornaghi Jr, et al., 2020). Stage II (150–300 °C), ~ 20 wt% loss, corresponding to decomposition of hemicellulose (200 –280 °C) and initial cleavage of amorphous cellulose (280 –300 °C). The lower onset relative to treated fibers arises from the high hemicellulose content and inherent structural disorder in untreated fibers (Mudoj & Sinha, 2024). Stage III (300 –500 °C), ~ 25 wt% loss, attributed to cellulose pyrolysis and partial lignin breakdown, culminating in char formation (Prasad et al., 2020). The residual mass at 600 °C (~ 45 wt%) indicates a substantial yield of inorganic ash and carbonaceous char (Llorens, et al., 2023), typical for untreated palm fibers rich in mineral content and lignin matrix.

Figure 3: TGA and DSC curves of untreated FTPTF

CONCLUSION

The result of the study presents a comprehensive extraction and characterization of the Fishtail Palm Trunk Fibers revealing its fundamental properties. Chemical analysis revealed FPTF to have high cellulose (58.05 wt%), moderate hemicellulose (14.03 wt%), lignin (12.12 wt%), wax (0.72 wt%) and ash (3.81 wt%) content compared with other natural fibers. The result also shows that, the fibre have a relatively low density of 1.31 g/cm³ making them suitable as lightweight reinforcements in composites processing and other applications requiring low density fibres. The fibre present some improved mechanical properties in terms of tensile strength of (210 MPa), indicating that the fibre can withstand stress and strain, ensuring the longevity of the products in textiles, composite and rope processing.

FTIR confirmed the presence of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, with peaks at 3341, 2918, and 1580 cm⁻¹ representing O-H, C-H, and C = C bonds, respectively. Morphology of the fibre indicates features that create a high-surface-energy, roughened profile. TGA and DSC results showed FPTF thermal stability and robust reinforcement enabling potential processing into composites.

In summary, the overall results reveal the extensive characterization of Fishtail palm trunk fibre's chemical composition, mechanical properties, structure and morphology. These properties demonstrate their potential as a sustainable reinforcement for bio composites, offering advantages over synthetic fibers.

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